
Research Article

A new combination in *Hertia* (Asteraceae)

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Abstract: *Cineraria alata* L.f. is transferred to *Hertia* Less. as *Hertia alata* (L.f.) R.Kr.Singh. Lectotypes are also designated for the names *Cineraria alata* L.f. and *C. spathulata* Lam.

Keywords: Cape of Good Hope, Cape Province, *Cineraria alata*, Lectotype, South Africa

Introduction

The genus *Hertia* Less. comprises nine species distributed in North Africa, South Africa and Western Asia (POWO, 2025). The vegetative and floral characters of *Cineraria alata* L.f., as described in the protologue corresponds well with the diagnostic features of *Hertia*, supporting its transfer to that genus.

Some online databases indicate that the combination *Hertia alata* (L.f.) Kuntze was published by C.E.O. Kuntze (1843–1907). However, no evidence of such a combination could be traced in Kuntze's works. Therefore, the new combination is validly published here. Lectotypes are designated here for the names *Cineraria alata* L.f. and *C. spathulata* Lam. in accordance with the guidelines and recommendations of Article 9 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2025).

New combination

Hertia alata (L.f.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Cineraria alata* L.f., Suppl. Pl. 374. 1782. *Doria alata* (L.f.) Thunb., Nov. Gen. Pl. [Thunberg] 12: 164. 1800. *Othonna alata* (L.f.) Sch.Bip., Flora 27: 769. 1844. *Othonnopsis alata* (L.f.) Benth. & Hook.f. ex B.D.Jacks., Index Kew. 1: 789. 1893.

Figure 1: Lectotype of *Cineraria alata* L.f. (LINN-HS1321-11, © Herbarium, Linnean Society of London)

Figure 2: Isolectotype of *Cineraria alata* L.f. (S-G-2133, © Department of Botany, Swedish Museum of Natural History)

Figure 3: Lectotype of *Cineraria spathulata* Lam. (P00342414, © Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris)

Lectotype (designated here): South Africa, Cape, *C.P. Thunberg s.n.* (LINN-HS1321-11, Figure 1!); isolectotypes S07-7561!, S07-7562!, S07-7563!, S-G-2133! (Figure 2), SBT13681!, SBT13682!, SBT13683!.

= *Cineraria spathulata* Lam., Encycl. [J. Lamarck & al.] 2: 8. 1786.

Lectotype (designated here or perhaps holotype): South Africa, Cape of Good Hope, *s.d.*, *Anon. s.n.* (P00342414!, Figure 3).

Distribution: South Africa (Cape Province).

Notes: *Cineraria alata* was described by Linnaeus filius (1782) based on specimens collected by C.P. Thunberg from the Cape region of South Africa. No holotype was designated in the protologue, nor was any herbarium specified, which was consistent with the taxonomic practice of that period. Linnaeus filius' types are known to be held at LINN and S (Stafleu & Cowan, 1981). Eight specimens of *C. alata* collected by C.P. Thunberg from Cape, South Africa were traced (LINN-HS1321-11, S07-7561, S07-7562, S07-7563, S-G-2133, SBT13681, SBT13682 and SBT13683). Among these, specimen LINN-HS1321-11 is the best preserved and is designated here as the lectotype as it agrees well with the protologue.

For *Cineraria spathulata* Lam., only a single specimen (P00342414) could be traced in the Lamarck Herbarium at P. As it remains uncertain whether Lamarck examined a single specimen or multiple specimens while preparing the protologue, specimen P00342414 is designated here as the lectotype, although it may ultimately prove to be the holotype.

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References

- Linnaeus, f. (1782). Supplementum plantarum systematis vegetabilium editionis decimae tertiae, generum plantarum editiones sextae, et specierum plantarum editionis secundae. Impensis Orphanotrophei, Brunsvigae.
- POWO. (2025). Plants of the World Online. Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew. Available from: <http://www.plantsoftheworldonline.org/> (accessed 18 November 2025).
- Stafleu, F.A. and Cowan, R.S. (1981). Taxonomic literature, vol. 3. Bohn, Scheltema & Holkema, Utrecht.
- Turland, N.J., Wiersema, J.H., Barrie, F.R., Greuter, W., Hawksworth, D.L., Herendeen, P.S., Knapp, S., Kusber, W.-H., Li, D.-Z., Marhold, K., May, T.W., McNeill, J., Monro, A.M., Prado, J., Price,

M.J. and Smith, G.F. (2018). International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code). *Regnum Vegetabile* 159. Koeltz Botanical Books, Glashütten.
<https://doi.org/10.12705/Code.2018>